

HIPPARCOS :-

GRID SPECIFICATIONS

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The following specifications are preliminary and tentative, since the optical system and grid parameters have not yet been fully optimised, and some specifications may be relaxed if serious manufacturing problems are encountered. The assumed scale is $11.92 \mu\text{m}/\text{arcsec}$ ($f_{\text{eq}} = 2459 \text{ mm}$).

Overall dimension of main grid + star mapper : c.a. $40 \times 55 \text{ mm}$

Support : curved focal surface ($R = -1189 \text{ mm}$)

Pattern : Main grid : linear, parallel slits, slit width = $3.28 \mu\text{m}$
period = $13.11 \mu\text{m}$

(N.B. period = distance between centres of adjacent slits.)
See Fig. 1.

Star mapper : linear slits, 8 "vertical" (parallel to main grid slits),
& inclined $\pm 45^\circ$. See Fig. 1-2.

The separation between main grid and star mapper should be the least possible, as determined by the relay optics configuration.

The pattern shown in Figs. 1-2 is assumed to be the plane projection of the true (curved) pattern. (This may be subject to revision.)

Acceptable tolerances:

- for the overall linear scale: $< 1\%$
- typical deviation of any edge position from nominal. (after adjusting for scale error): $< 0.5 \mu\text{m rms}$ (large scale distortion)
- defect on parallelism between adjacent slits: $< 0.2 \mu\text{m}$
- max 5 outgrowths + holes ($\geq 3 \mu\text{m } \phi$) per edge.
- edge sharpness (from 0.1 to 0.9 of maximum transmittance): $< 0.5 \mu\text{m}$
- opacity of dark bands: > 2.5 (i.e. $T_{\text{min}} < 10^{-2.5}$)
- transmittance of slits: > 0.99 (excluding glass support)
- average ratio $\frac{\text{slit width}}{\text{grid period}} = \frac{r}{s} = 0.25 \pm 0.01$.

(This is both an absolute tolerance and a tolerance on local deviations.)

See also Fig. 3 for definition of edge sharpness etc.

MAIN GRID AND STAR MAPPER CONFIGURATION (79-06-18 L.L.)

freq = 2459 mm
 scale: 11.92 μm/arcsec

N.B. The minimum separation (X) between main grid and star mapper is determined by the relay optics configuration; probably of the order of 10' will be necessary.

For details of star mapper, see separate sheet.

Radius of curvature - 1189 mm.

Main grid (for IDT), consisting of ~2945 parallel slits

FIGURE 7

COARSE STAR
MAPPER

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FIGURE 2

grid period (s)

FIGURE 3

Ideal grid:

- $S = 13.11 \mu\text{m} (1.1)$
- $r = 3.28 \mu\text{m} (0.275)$
- $T_{\text{max}} = 1$
- $T_{\text{min}} = 0$
- $\Delta_{0.1} = \Delta_{0.9} = 0$

Tolerances:

- $T_{\text{max}} > 0.99 T_{\text{glass support}}$
- $T_{\text{min}} < 10^{-2.5}$
- $\Delta_{0.1} \Delta_{0.9} < 0.25 \mu\text{m}$

(Each tolerance corresponds to a $\leq 1\%$ increase of photon-statistical variance.)

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